

Supplementary Materials

¹H NMR METABOLOMICS AND MOLECULAR NETWORKING REVEAL RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN METABOLITE PROFILE AND ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY OF MALAYSIAN STINGLESS BEE HONEY

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Figure S1. PCA loading plots of metabolites identified on different stingless bee honey species

Figure S2. Molecular Networking (MN) established using MS/MS data from the LC-MS/MS analysis of *T. apicalis* honey. Selected nodes and cluster have been zoomed in at below.

HoneyA_switch #6203 RT: 23.50 AV: 1 NL: 7.94E
T: FTMS - c ESI d Full ms2 271.0613@hcd30.00 [50.0000-295.0000]

Figure S3. MS spectrum of Naringenin

HoneyA_switch #6195 RT: 23.47 AV: 1 NL: 2.26E
T: FTMS - c ESI d Full ms2 287.0926@hcd30.00 [50.0000-310.0000]

Figure S4. MS spectrum of Eriodictyol

HoneyA_switch#3627 RT: 13.85 AV: 1 NL: 3.43E
T: FTMS - c ESI d Full ms2 433.1149@hcd30.00 [50.0000-460.0000]

Figure S5. MS spectrum of Naringenin-7-O-glucoside

HoneyA_switch#4148 RT: 15.82 AV: 1 NL: 5.53E
T: FTMS - c ESI d Full ms2 403.1040@hcd30.00 [50.0000-430.0000]

Figure S6. MS spectrum of Naringenin-7-O-beta-D-xylopyranoside

HoneyA_switch#4301 RT: 16.40 AV: 1 NL: 4.88E
T: FTMS - c ESI d Full ms2 447.0944@hcd30.00 [50.0000-475.0000]

Figure S7. MS spectrum of Quercitrin

HoneyA_switch#5781 RT: 21.93 AV: 1 NL: 3.64E5
T: FTMS - c ESI d Full ms2 301.0355@hcd30.00 [50.0000-325.0000]

Figure S8. MS spectrum of Quercetin

HoneyA_switch #5788 RT: 21.95 AV: 1 NL: 1.29f
T: FTMS - c ESI'd Full ms2 285.0405@hcd30.00 [50.0000-310.0000]

Figure S9 MS spectrum of Luteolin

HoneyA_switch #6261 RT: 23.70 AV: 1 NL: 7.54f
T: FTMS - c ESI'd Full ms2 285.0406@hcd30.00 [50.0000-310.0000]

Figure S10. MS spectrum of Kaempferol

HoneyA_switch#6347 RT: 24.01 AV: 1 NL: 3.04E
T: FTMS - c ESI d Full ms2 315.0512@hcd30.00 [50.0000-340.0000]

Figure S11. MS spectrum of Isorhamnetin

Table S1. Identification of metabolites characteristics in stingless bee honey samples

No	Metabolite	δ H	Availability
1	2-Hydroxymethyl-5-furfural	9.44 (s), 7.52 (d, J= 4.0 Hz), 6.66 (d, J= 4.0 Hz)	All
2	Trigonelline	9.10 (s), 8.82 (m), 8.07 (m)	<i>L. canifrons</i>
3	Formic acid	8.40 (s)	All
4	4-Hydroxymandelic acid	7.47 (d, J= 4.0 Hz), 6.30 (d, J= 4.0 Hz)	<i>H. itama</i>
5	Phenylalanine	7.41 (m), 7.36 (m), 7.31 (m), 3.11 (m)	All
6	Tyrosine	7.17 (d, J= 8.0 Hz), 6.87(d, J= 8.0 Hz), 3.44 (s, overlapped)	All
7	Sucrose	5.42 (d, J= 4.0 Hz), 4.21 (d, J= 8.0 Hz)	All
8	Maltose	5.38 (d, J= 4.0 Hz), 5.22 (d, overlapped), 4.21 (d, J= 8.0 Hz)	All
9	Arabinose	5.28 (d, J= 4.0 Hz), 5.23 (d, overlapped)	All
10	Glucose	5.21 (d, J= 4.0 Hz), 4.63 (d, J= 8.0 Hz), 3.20 (m)	All
11	Fucose	5.15 (d, J= 4.0 Hz), 4.57 (d, J= 8.0 Hz)	All
12	Rhamnose	5.1 (d, J= 4.0 Hz), 1.27 (d, J= 6.8 Hz)	All
13	1-O- α -D-Glucopyranosyl- β -D-fructopyranose (trehalulose isomers)	4.95 (d, J= 3.6 Hz), 4.07 (dd, overlap), 4.02 (d, J= 1.2 Hz)	All
14	1-O- α -D-Glucosylpyranosyl- β -D-fructofuranose (trehalulose isomers)	4.98 (d, J= 3.6 Hz), 4.15 (d, J= 8.0 Hz), 4.13 (d, overlap)	All
15	Fructose	4.09 (m), 4.04 (m), 3.98 (m)	All
16	Sarcosine	2.73 (s)	All
17	Citric acid	2.78 (d, J= 16.0 Hz), 2.68 (d, J= 16.0 Hz)	All
18	Glutamine	2.48 (m), 2.15 (m)	All
19	Glutamic acid	2.40 (m), 2.04 (m)	All
20	Lactic acid	4.10 (m), 1.34 (d, J= 6.8 Hz)	All
21	Threonine	4.26 (m, overlapped), 1.30 (d, J= 6.8 Hz)	All
22	Acetic acid	2.00 (s)	All
23	4-Hydroxy-L-proline	4.32 (m), 2.38 (m), 2.14 (m)	All
24	Alanine	1.46 (d, J= 7.2 Hz)	All
25	2-Phenylpropionic acid	1.42 (d, J= 6.8 Hz)	All
26	Ethanol	3.65 (m, overlapped), 1.16 (t, J= 7.2)	All
27	Methylmalonic acid (MMA)	3.19 (q, overlapped), 1.22 (d, J= 7.2 Hz)	All
28	Propylene glycol	1.12 (d, J= 6.4 Hz)	All
29	3-Hydroxyisobutyric acid	1.06 (d, J= 7.2 Hz)	All
30	Valine	1.02 (d, J= Hz), 0.97 (d, J= Hz)	All
31	Isoleucine	0.99 (d, J= Hz), 0.91 (t, overlapped)	All
32	Leucine	0.94 (m), 1.73 (m)	All
33	Unknown	8.65 (m)	<i>T. binghami</i> , <i>L. canifrons</i>
34	Unknown	6.69 (dd, J= 1.6, 3.6 Hz)	<i>H. itama</i>
35	Unknown	7.82 (d, J=1.6 Hz)	<i>H. itama</i>
36	Unknown	5.48 (d, J= 3.6 Hz)	All

Table S2. Compounds identified of *T. apicalis* honey sample by LC-MS/MS analysis

Peak num	t _r (min)	Molecular ion	Ionization mode	Mass error	MS/MS fragments (m/z)	Identification
1.	1.221	527.1561	[M+Na] ⁺	0.0021	347, 203	Raffinose
2.	1.24	341.1085	[M-H] ⁻	0.0004	179, 161, 119, 101	α,α-Trehalose
3.	1.37	181.0712	[M-H] ⁻	0.0006	101, 89, 71, 59	D-Mannitol
4.	1.40	341.1094	[M-H] ⁻	0.0005	89, 71,59	α -Lactose
5.	1.52	341.1092	[M-H] ⁻	0.0003	179,119, 90	α-Mannobiose
6.	1.60	195.0506	[M-H] ⁻	0.0004	129,75	D-Mannoric acid
7.	1.60	341.1093	[M-H] ⁻	0.0004	89, 71, 59	D-Maltose
8.	1.70	195.0508	[M-H] ⁻	0.0002	129, 103, 75	Gluconic acid
9.	1.97	173.0446	[M-H] ⁻	0.001	155, 129	Shikimic acid
10.	2.77	164.0709	[M-H] ⁻	0.0007	147,72	L-Phenylalanine
11.	2.81	166.0859	[M+H] ⁺	0.0003	131, 120, 104	L-Phenylalanine
12.	3.56	229.1543	[M+H] ⁺	0.0004	116, 86	Pro-Leu
13.	5.60	181.0499	[M-H] ⁻	0.0007	136, 119	4-Hydroxyphenyllactic acid
14.	10.14	387.1662	[M-H] ⁻	0.0001	342, 163, 145	Tuberonic acid glucoside
15.	10.81	172.097	[M-H] ⁻	0.0009	130	Acetylleucine
16.	11.00	211.1437	[M+H] ⁺	0.0004	183, 114	cis-Cyclo(leucyl-prolyl)
17.	11.5	249.1344	[M-H] ⁻		101, 85	2-Methylbutyl beta-D-glucopyranoside
18.	11.58	172.0972	[M-H] ⁻	0.0007	130	N-Acetylleucine
19.	11.77	371.0987	[M-H] ⁻	0.0367	249,121	2-O-Caffeoylglucaric acid
20.	12.09	165.0547	[M-H] ⁻	0.001	147,72	(S)-3-Phenyllactic acid
21.	12.23	353.1003	[M-H] ⁻	0.0125	165, 147,119	Caffeoylquinic acid
22.	12.39	353.1006	[M-H] ⁻	0.0125	165,147,119	Caffeoylquinic acid derivative
23.	12.52	565.1539	[M+H] ⁺	0.0013	427, 379	Apigenin 7-apiofuranosyl-(1->6)-glucoside
24.	12.84	206.0815	[M-H] ⁻	0.0008	164, 147	N-Acetyl-L-phenylalanine
25.	12.95	236.0925	[M-H] ⁻	0.0149	88	N-Acetyl-D-galactosaminic acid
26.	13.12	208.0964	[M+H] ⁺	0.0004	120	N-Acetyl-L-phenylalanine
27.	13.81	273.0753	[M+H] ⁺	0.0004	153, 119	Naringenin

28.	13.85	433.1149	[M-H] ⁻	0.0007	271, 151	Naringenin-7-O-glucoside
29.	14.22	433.1146	[M-H] ⁻	0.0006	271, 151	Naringenin 4'-O-glucoside
30.	14.28	431.0988	[M-H] ⁻	0.0004	271, 151	Apigenin 4'-glucoside
31.	14.35	273.0752	[M+H] ⁺	0.0005	271, 151	Naringenin chalcone
32.	14.79	204.0666	[M-H] ⁻	0.0000	158	Indole-3-lactic acid
33.	14.85	623.1634	[M-H] ⁻	0.0016	285	Kaempferol 5-methyl ether 3-galactoside-4'-glucoside
34.	15.58	359.1508	[M-H] ⁻	0.0008	313, 109	Isolariciresinol
35.	15.82	403.104	[M-H] ⁻		271, 151	Naringenin-7-O-beta-D- xylopyranoside
36.	16.40	447.0944	[M-H] ⁻	0.0011	301, 271, 151	Quercitrin
37.	16.55	301.0724	[M-H] ⁻	0.0008	273,109	4',5,7-Trihydroxy-3- methoxyflavanone
38.	16.85	187.0972	[M-H] ⁻	0.0004	169, 125	Azelaic acid
39.	17.64	251.0461	[M+H] ⁺	0.0066	251, 157, 95	Diphenyl phosphate
40.	18.16	361.1663	[M-H] ⁻	0.0006	315, 179, 165, 121	Secoisolariciresinol
41.	18.25	165.055	[M-H] ⁻	0.0007	147, 121, 119	3-Phenyllactic acid
42.	18.64	461.2401	[M-H] ⁻	0.1312	415, 301, 147	Quercetin 3-methyl ether 7-rhamnoside
43.	19.14	327.0722	[M-H] ⁻	0.0000	283, 223, 151	Bergenin
44.	20.14	439.1873	[M-H] ⁻	1.026	289, 247, 149,134	Diferuloylputrescine
45.	20.4	221.1895	[M+H] ⁺	0.0005	203, 107	Nootkatol
46.	21.4	287.0564	[M-H] ⁻	0.0004	151, 135, 107	(+)-dihydrokaempferol
47.	21.49	287.0565	[M-H] ⁻	0.0003	151, 135, 107	Measopin
48.	21.93	301.0355	[M-H] ⁻	0.0001	179, 151, 121, 107	Quercetin
49.	21.95	285.0405	[M-H] ⁻	0.0000	151, 107	Luteolin
50.	21.96	283.061	[M-H] ⁻	0.0002	268, 240	Glycitein
51.	22.54	221.1897	[M+H] ⁺	0.0004	161, 147, 109	(-)-Caryophyllene oxide
52.	23.47	287.0926	[M-H] ⁻	0.0365	151, 135, 109	Eriodictyol
53.	23.50	271.0613	[M-H] ⁻	0.0001	151, 119, 107	Naringenin
54.	23.51	271.0593	[M+H] ⁺	0.0008	153, 119, 107	Genistein
55.	23.58	269.0456	[M-H] ⁻	0.0000	151, 107	Apigenin
56.	23.61	301.0717	[M-H] ⁻	0.0001	151, 107	Hesperetin
57.	23.70	285.0406	[M-H] ⁻	0.0001	151, 121, 109	Kaempferol
58.	23.74	219.1736	[M+H] ⁺	0.0007	201, 123, 83	Nookatone

59.	23.76	287.054	[M+H] ⁺	0.0010	153, 121, 109	Kaempferol
60.	23.96	317.0645	[M+H] ⁺	0.0011	153, 121	Isorhamnetin
61.	24.01	315.0512	[M-H] ⁻	0.0002	151, 107	Isorhamnetin
62.	24.77	187.1335	[M-H] ⁻	0.0005	141, 59	10-Hydroxydecanoic acid
63.	27.77	327.0771	[M+H] ⁺	0.0010	233, 153	Triphenyl phosphate
64.	29.94	425.3763	[M+H] ⁺		231, 109	(4aS,5R,6S,8aS)-5-[(3E)-5-methoxy-3-methyl-5-oxopent-3-en-1-yl]-5,6,8a-trimethyl-3,4,4a,5,6,7,8,8a-octahydronaphthalene-1-carboxylic acid
65.	30.76	311.2935	[M+H] ⁺	0.0010	116, 102, 88	Ethyl oleate
66.	31.80	457.3663	[M+H] ⁺	0.0013	189, 136, 121, 109	Oleanolic acid
